

A recurrent formula inspired by Rowland's formula and based on Smarandache function which might be a criterion for primality

Marius Coman
Bucuresti, Romania
email: mariuscoman13@gmail.com

Abstract. Studying the two well known recurrent relations with the exceptional property that they generate only values which are equal to 1 or are primes, id est the formula which belongs to Eric Rowland and the one that belongs to Benoit Cloitre, I managed to discover a formula based on Smarandache function, from the same family of recurrent relations, which, instead to give a prime value for any input, seems to give the same value, 2, if and only if the value of the input is a prime. I name this relation the Coman-Smarandache criterion for primality and the exceptions from this rule, if they exist, Coman-Smarandache pseudoprimes.

Conjecture

Let $f(1) = 1$ and $f(n) = S(f(n - 1)) + \text{lcm}[n, S(f(n - 1))]$, where S is the Smarandache function and lcm the least common multiple. Then the value of the function $g(n) = f(n)/S(f(n - 1))$ is equal to 2 if and only if n is an odd prime.

Verifying the conjecture

(up to $n = 17$)

: $f(2) = 1 + \text{lcm}[2, 1] = 3;$	then $g(2) = 3/1 = 3;$
: $f(3) = 3 + \text{lcm}[3, 3] = 6;$	then $g(3) = 6/3 = \mathbf{2};$
: $f(4) = 3 + \text{lcm}[4, 3] = 15;$	then $g(4) = 15/3 = 5;$
: $f(5) = 5 + \text{lcm}[5, 5] = 10;$	then $g(5) = 10/5 = \mathbf{2};$
: $f(6) = 5 + \text{lcm}[6, 5] = 35;$	then $g(6) = 35/5 = 7;$
: $f(7) = 7 + \text{lcm}[7, 7] = 14;$	then $g(7) = 14/7 = \mathbf{2};$
: $f(8) = 7 + \text{lcm}[8, 7] = 63;$	then $g(8) = 63/7 = 9;$
: $f(9) = 7 + \text{lcm}[9, 7] = 70;$	then $g(9) = 70/7 = 10;$
: $f(10) = 7 + \text{lcm}[10, 7] = 77;$	then $g(10) = 77/7 = 11;$
: $f(11) = 11 + \text{lcm}[11, 11] = 22;$	then $g(11) = 22/11 = \mathbf{2};$
: $f(12) = 11 + \text{lcm}[12, 11] = 143;$	then $g(12) = 143/11 = 13;$
: $f(13) = 13 + \text{lcm}[13, 13] = 26;$	then $g(13) = 26/13 = \mathbf{2};$
: $f(14) = 13 + \text{lcm}[14, 13] = 195;$	then $g(14) = 195/13 = 15;$
: $f(15) = 13 + \text{lcm}[15, 13] = 208;$	then $g(15) = 208/13 = 16;$
: $f(16) = 13 + \text{lcm}[16, 13] = 221;$	then $g(16) = 221/13 = 17;$
: $f(17) = 17 + \text{lcm}[17, 17] = 17;$	then $g(17) = 34/17 = \mathbf{2}.$

Note

It can be seen that, in the verified cases, the value of $g(n)$ is equal to 2 if and only if n is odd prime; the value of $g(n)$ in any other case (for any other n) beside $f(1) = 1$ and $f(p) = 2$, where p is odd prime, is equal to $n + 1$.

Note

The function $g(n) = f(n)/S(f(n - 1)) - 1$, where $f(n) = f(n - 1) + \text{lcm}[n, f(n - 1)]$ might also be interesting to study as a prime generating formula, as it gives prime values (i.e. 5, 17, 23, 191, 383) for the following consecutive values of n : 4, 5, 6, 7, 8; however, for $n = 9$ the value obtained is a semiprime and for $n = 10$ is not even obtained an integer value, because m is not always divisible by $S(m)$ so $f(n)$, which is always divisible by $f(n - 1)$, is not always divisible by $S(f(n - 1))$.

References:

1. Rowland, Eric, *A simple prime-generating recurrence*;
2. Peterson, Ivars, *A new formula for generating primes*;
3. Shevelev, Vladimir, *Generalizations of the Rowland Theorem*.